

Towards a Bayesian Digital Twin of the Ocean: Estimating Underwater Object Parameters

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Abstract—Digital twins of the ocean are becoming increasingly important not only for physical offshore assets but also for maintenance of the ecosystem and climate change mitigation. Since the ocean is a domain fraught with uncertainties, when modeling the environment, digital twins must incorporate this lack of knowledge. This work presents how such digital twin can be formulated as Bayesian digital twins of the ocean and the applicability of probabilistic programming languages as framework for implementing them.

Index Terms—Bayesian inference, digital twin, probabilistic programming languages.

I. INTRODUCTION

Suppose, we have a system able to detect location and type of underwater objects, e.g., a sonar based object detector. Each observation contains a location estimate and an estimated type of the object, resulting in an overall dataset as shown in Figure 1. As all data is collected via sensors, the measurements are noisy. Additionally, the identities of the objects are not observable, meaning correspondence between object and observation is unknown. In this paper, we present a sound approach to analyse the data with respect to a probabilistic domain model.

Fig. 1. 1000 object observations corresponding to 6 objects with 3 classes. Reefcones, Tetrapods and Reefrings are common human-made objects that are located at the seabed of the Digital Ocean Lab, Nienhagen, Germany.

Digital twins of the ocean possess immense potential not only for the analysis of physical off-shore assets but also for supporting ecosystem maintenance and climate change mitigation [1]. The key tasks, which define the digital twin,

consist of: collecting data, constructing a digital image of the environment, updating the image with new information, and inferring valuable insights. The new findings can then be incorporated into the decision-making processes, which in turn influences new incoming data – creating a continuous cycle.

Because of the complexity of the ocean as an ecosystem, the interrelations and challenging to impossible observability, models of the ocean are not deterministic and do not give a perfect rendering of the environment. Thus, digital twins in the maritime domain need to account for the model uncertainties [2].

Recent works already describe digital twins of physical assets as Bayesian networks and inference problems. They represent entities of the environment as random variables and their dependencies as conditional probability distributions [3]–[5]. Hence, the *Bayesian digital twin* formulates the problem of keeping a belief of the system, inferring and tracking unobservable entities. Since Bayesian inference becomes intractable in complex domains, tailored inference algorithms are developed for a specific problem.

To first find the probabilistic structure of the domain and to rapidly prototype the Bayesian digital twin, probabilistic programming languages (PPLs) serve to be an advisable tool [6]–[9]. PPLs offer the ability to describe stochastic processes (the digital twin) by providing the expressiveness of general-purpose programming languages and predefined libraries of distributions to sample from. They provide off-the-shelf inference methods to approximate latent variables and to correct the prior belief of the digital twin. The updated belief of the system can then assist decision making by humans or function as the system state for automated optimal decision making methods [2].

In this work, we model and implement the problem of inferring the location and class of objects from noisy, ambiguous, mixed discrete-continuous observations. We empirically show the impact of the model specification in terms of a diverging observation model and the challenges that arise concerning the label switching problem caused by the structural non-identifiability in the model.

II. RELATED WORK

A concept of a digital twin as dynamic Bayesian network (DBN) was given by [10]. The abstraction of the twin uses a probabilistic graphical model including decision variables. The motivation is to give a mathematical sound way at scale instead

of on-off digital twins. The model consists of a physical state, observational data, the digital state, control inputs, quantities of interest and rewards. The authors include of [10] an example that can be solved as forward filtering problem using particle filter and Kalman filter.

One use of DBNs as digital twin is to describe the current state of physical assets. In [11], the structural health of an aircraft is tracked. The authors build a DBN that models the relationships between variables, both continuous and discrete. They use particle filtering as inference method. In [12], the authors use a Gaussian particle filter for inference in the DBN, and tackle the problem of inferring hidden states, as well as unknown model parameters simultaneously. To improve inference performance, they introduce kernel smoothing to control the variance of the particle set and avoid divergence.

Recent works exploit PPLs for certain domain specific models or digital twins. In the domain of autonomous cars and robots, the domain-specific PPL Scenic [13] is able to sample scenes from arbitrary distributions specifying the properties of the scene. The authors of [14] create a digital twin of an outdoor road and use Scenic to generate test scenarios for safety investigations.

PPLs also allow for modelling the connection of multiple digital twins. The authors of [15] connect the digital twins of individual cardiovascular systems via an hierarchical Bayesian model. This also allows for incorporating knowledge and exchanging information between the models, resulting in better parameter estimations. The model was implemented in the PPL Stan [6]. Stan is used in [16] for implementing a surplus production model, linking abundance and removal of marine protected endangered or threatened species. The task is to investigate different harvest control rules.

Stan specifies probabilistic models by imperatively defining the log-density and inferring parameters that are conditioned on the data by e.g. Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods, such as the No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) [17].

NUTS is an adaptive variant of the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) algorithm [18] that does not require user tuning. HMC is an MCMC algorithm that uses Hamiltonian dynamics for the proposals which yields better state space exploration in comparison to standard random-walk proposals. However, the performance is highly sensitive to two user-specified parameters.

The aforementioned methods work only for continuous state spaces. In most popular PPLs, discrete variables are marginalized out [6], [7], [9]. The mixed HMC algorithm (mHMC) [19] addresses this limitation via updating discrete and continuous variables in a tandem, i.e. updating both simultaneously by embedding the discrete variable in a continuum. The mHMC method is available in the PPL NumPyro [8].

The following sections show how a digital twin, formalized as a probabilistic graphical model, can be implemented in the PPL NumPyro. Given an example domain, the resulting model and its parametrization, we show how the model translates into PPL program code and evaluate off-the-shelf inference methods on the domain specific example.

TABLE I
DESCRIPTION AND DOMAIN OF PARAMETERS AND VARIABLES OF THE MODEL.

Variable	Domain	Description
K	\mathbb{N}	Number of Objects
N	\mathbb{N}	Number of Classes
T	\mathbb{N}	Number of Observations
D	\mathbb{N}	Dimensions of Location
C_k	$1:N$	Class of Object k
μ_k	\mathbb{R}^D	Location of Object k
Z_t	$1:K$	Object seen at time t
C'_t	$1:N$	Class seen at time t
L_t	\mathbb{R}^D	Location seen at time t
α	Δ^N	Parameter of Class prior distribution
μ_0	\mathbb{R}^D	Mean of Location prior distribution
Σ_0	$\mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$	Covariance matrix of Location prior distribution
π	Δ^K	Parameter of prior Object allocation
β_n	Δ^N	Observation error of Class detection
Σ	$\mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$	Observation noise of Location detection

III. BAYESIAN MODELING

The digital twin of our domain is depicted as a Bayesian network in Figure 2 and abbreviations and domains of the variables are explained in Table I. There are K many objects that can have one of N possible classes and have T many observations of location and class. For simplicity, we assume 2-dimensional locations. The model consists of class $C_k=c_k$ and location $\mu_k=\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_k$ of an object k . We have an observation of the class $C'_t=c'_t$ and location $L_t=\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_t$ at timepoint t . The identity of the object $Z_t=k$ seen at time t is not observed and thus a latent variable. The domain factors are parameterized in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Graphical model of the Bayesian network with discrete and continuous multi-entity observations and a possible instance of the observation model B and Σ .

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\mu_k = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}; \mu_0, \Sigma_0) &= \mathcal{N}(\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} | \mu_0, \Sigma_0) \\
 p(C_k = c; \alpha) &= \text{Cat}(c | \alpha) \\
 p(Z_t = k; \pi) &= \text{Cat}(k | \pi) \\
 p(L_t = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} | Z_t = k; \mu_k, \Sigma) &= \mathcal{N}(\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} | \mu_k, \Sigma) \\
 p(C'_t = c | Z_t = k, C_k = c_k; B_{c_k} = \beta_{c_k}) &= \text{Cat}(c | \beta_{c_k})
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 3. Parametrization of the domain.

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def model(K, T, L, C, alpha, mu0, Sigma0, Sigma, B, pi):
    with plate("objects", K):
        mu = sample("mu", MultivariateNormal(mu0, Sigma0))
        c = sample("c", Categorical(alpha))
    with plate("t", T):
        k = sample("z", Categorical(pi))
        sample("l", MultivariateNormal(mu[k], Sigma), obs=L)
        sample("c", Categorical(B[c[k]]), obs=C)
    return

```

Fig. 4. NumPyro implementation following the specification in Figure 3.

Note that μ_k is a domain variable (the location) and a distribution parameter for the factor $p(L_t = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} | Z_t = k; \mu_k, \Sigma)$. The parameters Σ and $B = [\beta_n]_{n=1}^N$ quantify the error of the observations. The N -valued vector β_n describes the accuracy of detecting class n . Figure 2 depicts an example of the B matrix. A column vector, e.g. β_{\star} , represents the certainty of the classification observation. Given the example B matrix of Figure 2, if our object k is a tetrapod $C_k = \star$, then observing an reefcone $C'_t = \blacktriangle$ has probability of 0.2:

$$p(C'_t = \blacktriangle | Z_t = k, C_k = \star; B_{\star} = \beta_{\star}) = \text{Cat}(\blacktriangle | \beta_{\star}) = 0.2 .$$

The matrix Σ represents the measurement noise of the location detection. Figure 2 depicts an example for such measurement noise. If we detect an object at location $L_t = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_t$ and the true location of the object k is at $\mu_k = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_k$, then the likelihood of the location observation L_t given the object k is given by:

$$p(L_t = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_t | Z_t = k; \mu_k, \Sigma) = \mathcal{N}(\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_t | \mu_k = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_k, \Sigma) .$$

Note that all distribution parameters except μ_k are given in this work. We assume these as external expert knowledge. The parameter α describes the prior distribution of the objects' classes, i.e. which object types are more common. The parameter π of the allocation variable Z_t represents the distribution of the data points, i.e. how many observations belong to each object. The location variable has a normal distributed prior. The parameter μ_0 and Σ_0 describe the common location and variance of unknown objects. The observation model B and Σ is the confidence of the object detector and might be given through evaluation of the detector and thus in this model fixed.

Given the observations $\mathcal{O} = (\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix}_t, c_t)_{t=1}^T$, we want to find the posterior expectation $\mathbb{E}[C_k, \mu_k, Z_t | \mathcal{O}]$ and the posterior distribution $p(C_k, \mu_k, Z_t | \mathcal{O})$, i.e. what are the most likely locations and classes of the objects as well as the allocation of the observation to the object. In sampling based inference, the posterior distribution is given by samples and expectations can be computed from those samples.

In sampling based PPLs, we have to define how to sample from such model and how the model is conditioned on the observations. Knowing the parameterization of the factors, we can directly implement this process in a sampling based framework.

We choose NumPyro as PPL because of the availability of mixed discrete-continuous inference methods, in particular the mixed Hamiltonian Markov Chain (mHMC).

Figure 4 depicts the model as NumPyro implementation. Note that each sample statement corresponds to exactly one equation of the domain specification (Figure 3). The *plate* primitive in NumPyro describes independent variables. The objects and observations are independent from each other. The *sample* statements with passed *obs* parameter condition the observation on the distribution and represent the likelihood function. PPLs offer inference methods which sample from the model such that they approximate the posterior distribution.

IV. EVALUATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF CHALLENGES

In the following, we evaluate the model by using NumPyro to infer the position and class of objects. The goal is to investigate the applicability of a PPL and how the observation model, that we assume as given, can impact the performance if it diverges from the true distribution of the data.

A. Experimental Setup

We implement the model from Figure 2 in the PPL NumPyro. To show the applicability of the PPL and the impact of the predefined constants, we conduct an empirical evaluation using mHMC.

As application domain, we use a subsection of the Digital Ocean Lab, Nienhagen, Germany¹. We add artificial noise to the data by adding correlation between the xy -coordinate, which may occur from the wave direction at the Baltic sea. We generate a total of $T=1000$ data points which are depicted in Figure 1. Due environmental conditions and different sensor modalities, we assume observations of an object that can have an error in the location estimate of more than one meter. At the seabed of the reef are mainly 3 types of objects: Tetrapods, Reefcones and Reefrings.

We have $K=6$ objects which can have one of $N=3$ classes. The constants π and α are set such that $p(Z_t; \pi)$ and $p(C_k; \alpha)$ are uniformly distributed. As normal distributed prior for the location, we calculate the maximum likelihood estimate of μ_0 and Σ_0 given the whole dataset \mathcal{O} .

For the observation model of C'_t , we choose β_n such that we detect the correct class of the object with 0.8 probability:

$$p(C'_t = c | Z_t = k, C_k = c_k; B_{c_k} = \beta_{c_k}) = \begin{cases} 0.8 & \text{if } c = c_k, \\ 0.1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Note that the generated data does not align with this assumption. We evaluate the impact of a varying location observation model that diverges from the true observation variance. We scale the location observation model $\Sigma = \epsilon \cdot \mathbb{I}$ by a factor ϵ , with \mathbb{I} denoting the identity matrix, giving:

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \epsilon \end{bmatrix} .$$

Here we assume a diagonal covariance matrix. In the generated data we have correlation between x and y .

We run 50 mHMC chains with 2000 warm-up steps and drawing 2000 samples. As parameters for the mHMC algorithm, the trajectory length is set to 1.2, target acceptance is

¹<https://www.riff-nienhagen.de/>

set to 0.8 and the number of discrete steps is 30 steps. Due to the error in location estimates, we vary ϵ between $1e^{-4}$ and 2 and the number of data points available between 10 and 1000.

We calculate the expected locations and classes $\mathbb{E}[\mu_k, C_k | \mathcal{O}]$ from the samples representing the posterior distribution $p(\mu_k, C_k | \mathcal{O})$. Next, we compute the Euclidean distance between the expectations and the true locations of the objects to evaluate the error in location estimation of the model. Here we have to deal with the problem of *label switching* [20] caused by the *structural non-identifiability* [21] in the model. There are $K!$ many permutations of the object's ordering that all lead to the same result.

As in reality we have to select a chain that yields the best estimation, we need a criterion to select this chain. We use the log-likelihood $\log p(\mathcal{O})$ to evaluate the expectation of locations and classes. Since, in the Bayesian context, we want to find the distribution of unknown variables and parameters given the data, the log-likelihood gives us insights of how well the expected estimates explain our data.

B. Results and Discussion

Fig. 5. Resulting distances for different variances ϵ . Each point depicts one mHMC chain and the average distance between the estimated and correct locations of the objects respectively. Red crosses represent the chain with the maximum log-likelihood.

Figure 5 depicts the average distance from estimated locations to the real locations of the objects for each chain. The figure shows two main insights: (1) with increasing ϵ , i.e. higher variance in the observation model, the distance increases; and (2) some chains have higher distances for the same ϵ . A higher variance means that the model's assumption diverges from the real distribution of the data, thus leading to estimates of the location that do not align with the real locations anymore. If two objects are close to each other and the observation model assumes high variances in the detection of objects, the model is trying to explain both objects with the same component k and thus the expectation of location μ_k is in between the two objects. Smaller variances result in the smallest distances, however the lower the variance, the more overconfident the model is, i.e. the variance of the samples' μ_k is close to 0. For high variances in the observation model on the other hand, the samples' location have high variances and may cover two objects. Additionally, the likelihood between optimal parameterization becomes smoother, which causes

samples of one component to visit different modes, i.e. the identities of objects switch within a chain. Thus, calculating expectations yield undesired results which is mainly caused here through the observation model that diverges from the real distribution of the data.

We can also observe that some chains settle at estimates that have higher variance. The model is prone to local optima thus some MCMC chains do not converge in the global optima. For our application, currently, we are only interested in the expected class and location of objects. The MCMC method, however, draws samples from the posterior distribution $p(\mu_k, C_k | \mathcal{O})$. Summarizing chains for models with many local modes and structural non-identifiability require infeasible-many chains to converge against the true posterior. Assume that the structural non-identifiability is not known and we want to explore them via MCMC. There are $6! = 720$ many orderings of the objects. The orderings are uniformly distributed and one chain only represents one ordering. Thus, summarizing the posterior via chains is in the most cases infeasible.

In Figure 5, patterns of the distances are observable. The chains with minimal distances show in two intervals, around 0.3 to 0.75 and 1.25 to 1.5, an increased gradient. The cause of them is in the state of this work unknown and needs further investigation.

The red crosses in Figure 5 display the chains with the maximum log-likelihood. We use the log-likelihood as criteria to select the best chain. For small variances, the chains with the maximum log-likelihood always yield a chain close to the best in terms of minimal distance. Note that the minimal distance of the location does not necessarily align with the maximum log-likelihood. Since we assume parameters like B or Σ as given and the data is generated from different parameters, our estimates slightly diverge. This is however a common problem if the model cannot cover the reality exactly. This especially happens for this model at high variances in the observation model. However, the log-likelihood in the case of this model selects for every ϵ a chain with the optima that we are interested in, i.e. a chain with minimal distance.

Figure 6 depicts in contrast to the number of available observations the performance with respect to the distances of location estimates, runtimes and class estimates. Figure 6 (a) shows the average distance between the location estimate per chain and the true location of the object. The distance decreases with increasing amount of data. The red crosses depict the best chain with respect to the maximum log-likelihood. As discussed before, the maximum log-likelihood also selects the chain close to the best in terms of minimal distance, even with fewer data points. The difference between the minimal distance of the chain with 80 data points and the chain with 1000 data points is around 0.18. Relatively speaking, the estimation with 80 observations is close to the estimation with 1000 observations. Figure 6 (a) also shows the behavior of converging in local optima.

Figure 6 (b) shows the runtime per chain. The measured time is the execution time of the warm-up and sampling phase of the mHMC. Overall, we can see a linear increase in runtime with increasing number of observations. The increase is caused

Fig. 6. Distance of location estimates, runtime and confidence about the objects true class versus number of observations. Each point depicts one mHMC chain. Red crosses represent the best chains with respect to the log-likelihood. (a) Each point depicts the average distance between the estimated and correct location of the objects respectively. (b) Runtime per chain versus increasing number of data points. (c) Average confidence about the class of the object. Each point depicts the mean probability of the true objects.

by the number of factors added to the likelihood function (see “t-plate” of the NumPyro model in Figure 4).

Figure 6 (c) depicts the average confidence about the true class. The expectation of the class of an object is the empirical distribution of the class over the 2000 samples. Given the expectation, we can select the probability of the actual true class of the object. We then calculate the mean probability over the objects, telling us, in average, how many samples have the correct class estimate. For 10 observations, estimating the class, given the observation model, is still uncertain. 80 and more observations yield results with chains having the correct class estimates across all objects. Some chains do not reach a confidence of 1, which is caused when one component covers more than one object, thus resulting in switching classes, or multiple components cover the same object, resulting in a possible false classification. The red crosses represent the chains with maximum log-likelihood. Except the model with 10 observations available, the selection yields always correct class estimates.

Using the log-likelihood as criterion for selecting the best estimation yields close to or the best estimation for this model. This is caused by the location being normally distributed around the mean at the true location and the model estimates this location (see parametrization in Figure 5). Therefore, the optimal location estimate, that maximizes the likelihood, is close to the true location. Note that taking the log-likelihood as selection criteria does not have to apply for any model.

V. FURTHER EXTENSIONS

Further extensions from the direction of this model can include the estimation of the number of objects. As of this work, we assumed the number of available objects as given and may not be known under some circumstances. The number of objects can, e.g., be modelled with a Dirichlet Process [22].

If parameters, e.g. of the observation model, are unknown or results are caused by observation models that do not represent the data good enough, they have to be estimated. We then have to treat them as random variables and choose an appropriate

prior and search for the posterior distribution of the parameters given the data. The model can be extended with the same strategy as for the location parameter. A comparison to the expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm is also of interest for parameter estimation, if we are only interested in point estimations (expectations of the parameters).

The applicability of different PPLs can be evaluated for estimating continuous parameters, as they all have different implementation strategies.

Digital twins are updated over time. Thus, for estimating parameters as incremental learning process, different strategies have to be adopted. This task can also be formulated as recursive Bayesian filtering problem. MCMC methods for incremental continuous learning [23] have to be extended for discrete spaces. Sequential Monte Carlo methods (also known as particle filter) can approximate the distribution of latent variables as particles which update over time with new incoming data. The EM algorithm can also be extended to recursively learn the parameters [24].

A combination of these extensions also have to deal with the “birth and death” of objects.

VI. CONCLUSION

By modelling a digital twin as probabilistic graphical model, this study presented the concept of a Bayesian digital twin and its implementation in a probabilistic programming language for inferring latent variables and correcting prior beliefs.

Given the problem of inferring the class and location of objects, we formulated the problem as probabilistic graphical model and gave a parameterized form of the model. The parametrization provides the layout for implementing the model and can almost directly be translated to a model in PPLs. Since the model deals with discrete and continuous variables, we used NumPyro’s implementation of the mixed discrete-continuous Hamiltonian Monte Carlo method. We evaluated the model under different noise levels of the location detection.

Results show that under the condition of the observation model diverging too far from the true distribution of the data, inference cannot find the distinct locations of the objects anymore. However, if close to the true observation noise, the locations' approximation is closer to true location. PPLs suffer from domain specific problems like label switching and local optima. If those properties of the model are not known beforehand, the inference results can lead to unexpected and unwanted estimations.

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